

Field Practice During the Covid-19 Pandemic: Are We Virtually and Digitally Ready?

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Abstract

Immense literature is available on advocating the significance of field work and there are no divided opinions about it. However, societal problems that require intervention never exhibit a set pattern. They not only take different forms but also increase in magnitude and complexity. The latest adversary to social work practice has been the COVID-19 pandemic. The reeling effect it has had on global economies who had been positioning themselves as almost indomitable, were also not spared. Social work is practiced across nations, irrespective of power or impoverishment. The new challenge owing to the pandemic was felt most in the field work component of social work education. This is not to deny that the practice itself was inundated with the challenges of technology and its accompanying issues. Digital inequalities, practitioners' own mental health issues, the fear of the slowly unfolding mystery of the virus and its unending mutations challenged one and all. The degrees were different as societies belong to different economies. This paper explores how social work practice and social work education was affected during the pandemic and how the digital route was adopted to flow with the tide. It underlines the requirements of emotional connect, confidentiality ethics, and private physical space to engage in digital conferencing with the clients. It also highlights the unique problems of field work education in remotely located places, where digital access is further impeded poor data receptivity.

Keywords: *Field work, social work practice, social work education, digital inequality, pandemic*

Introduction

The centrality of field work in social work education across the world needs no further scrutiny. It has always had a crucially defining place in its history, until today. The approach and criteria adopted may vary across geographies and institutions. Eleni Papouli (2014) says that the much-valued experiential learning actually takes place during field work. Shardlow & Doel (1996) have also pointed out that such experiential learning takes places in the classroom too via a range of interactions. Social work education thus necessarily banks on theories in the classroom as well as practice learning in the field. It can therefore be understood that field work education cannot be

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undermined and the pandemic induced challenges must not impinge itself upon the teaching learning quality and process.

As the pandemic ensued, a host of unforeseen challenges emerged in social work practice as well as education. The reasons are several. The digital divide was the most paramount amongst all. Across the world, hopping on to the online route was presented as the only solace towards 'being safe'. As physical distancing became the most preferred mode of social interaction, field work in social work education was being challenged by the virus on all fronts. Student learning has to take place within given time frames as per a given academic schedule. They are then to be assessed under given rigorous conditions. When the space for performing the given activity is itself inaccessible, how does one evaluate the performance? To make up for the lost physical space, the digital space was brought in. But how did it measure up as an alternative space for learning? Was it accessible? Was it equitable? Was it sufficient? These are the questions we seek to examine in this paper. It will also contextualise the Northeast region of India where internet connectivity is many times a woeful scenario. Additionally, the poverty levels here also impede access to the internet. To better understand the significance of the nuances and need for human connectivity in social work practice, we look at a few empirical studies. We then look at how field work education per se, which is an essential skill training for future practitioners, were carried out and the challenges faced therein.

Home Visits During the Pandemic

Home visits are a very essential practice measure in social work. Laura L. Cook and Danny Zschomler (2020) emphasize this, particularly in child and family social work. Working with children necessitates being closely engaged with them "physically, emotionally and cognitively" and be "intimate" with them. Ferguson (2018) and Baeza et al (2019) emphasizes the need for professional touch. Ferguson (2018), Cook (2020) and Saltiel and Lakey (2020) have also opined that the physical home environment is a pertinent factor that can influence the intervention work. Sensory perceptions and emotions together also play a vital role during home visits. Thus, it played hugely upon the professional capabilities of the social worker as the shift of engagement for intervention was extremely profound and sudden as well owing to the pandemic. Nonetheless, they talk about both the pros and cons of such a medium of practice.

Cook and Zschomler (2020) present their study in the aftermath of the sudden lockdown that was imposed in England. Except for very urgent visits, the

social workers had to make do with online interactions as per prevailing government protocols. They conducted in-depth interviews with 31 such social workers who had to undertake virtual home visits, and examined the avenues as well as challenges. As the digital replaced the physical world of contact, they report that initially the social workers expressed due concern regarding rapport building as they were not keen to let the computer screen come in between their relationships. But visible changes gradually occurred in their perspective towards online interaction. All the usual social media interactive platforms were used. Although such virtual visits could not completely serve as a mainstay, it no doubt helped a lot. They describe it as a “little and often” approach. An intermeshing of phone calls, texts, and video calls provided support to each format. It was also supplemented with necessary exchange of hard copy documents. Virtual sessions drew some unanticipated rewards too in terms of a wider engagement with the clients’ routine lives. Travel time being nullified helped the workers to remain enthused.

The emotional distance in the digital world of not being able to see, touch, and feel the subject of practice, inability to access the actual environment, which has a tremendous effect upon the person, were the limitations of the digital practice. Non-verbal cues were missed out. Confidentiality issues arose as one could not monitor the privacy or lack of it in such a platform. Besides, some issues could never garner the kind of response and results in an online mode as it required multiple sensitivities. Cases of trauma or personal shame could just not be dealt with effectively online. Besides all these, the problem of digital exclusion was also noted by Cook and Zschomler (2020).

Another very pertinent concern raised was that such virtual practices should not feed themselves into routine social work practice; and thus, give way to austerity measures, thereby impacting welfare aid. Lack of face-to-face interaction with colleagues, shortage of work space at home with full confidentiality ethics were additional problems. Their own mental fatigue was highlighted, owing to which performance may have been hampered. Noting the above findings, Cook and Zschomler (2020), therefore suggest that a hybrid model of virtual and face-to-face practice is best adopted in the wake of the pandemic.

Technology, The Pandemic, and Social Work Education

Kourgiantakis and Lee (2020) emphasize upon the need to acquire social work practice competencies that encompass self-awareness, self-reflection, cross-cultural understanding, integrating theory and practice, and adopting

the principles of social justice. Similarly, they too highlight the essence of field work in social work education. They also mention how cost-cutting measures were already affecting social work practice prior to the pandemic. With the sudden onset of the pandemic and the subsequently imposed lockdown, they cite the Canadian Association for Social Work Education (CASWE) 2020, where some had to discontinue field supervision while some others went digital. These resulted in a host of unforeseen challenges. Besides having to overhaul the field work component of the curriculum, other harsh realities ranged from overall general health to mental health issues of students, faculty, family members etc. People were grappling with economic upturns in the family, caregiving, loss and grief. They report that access to healthcare was also disturbingly inequitable.

They cite Knowles (2007) and Levin et al. (2018) to exemplify that the digital platform had always been an interface for learning earlier too. What was newly challenging was doing field work online. Such a platform lacked the necessary capacity to provide practice opportunities to the students. It consequently affected the evaluation formats and interactive spaces between the faculty and the learner. Levin et al. (2018) had also conducted a survey and found that although pathbreaking technological advancements are being made, the mood is still low towards online practice. They substantiate preference for faculty evaluation where physical learning was found more rewarding to the students.

Knowles (2007) raised several issues faced by educators and administrators in engaging with online practice. They categorised them into four groups: (1) pedagogical challenges (e.g. online relationship building, redesigning curricula and teaching methods), (2) professional challenges (e.g. alignment of e-learning with SW education, ethics, professionalism, and e-equity), (3) faculty challenges (e.g. time, workload, compensation, professional development, and technical support), and (4) administrative challenges (e.g. program structure and academic policies). Meanwhile, East et al. (2014) advocate developing online communities of practice to keep up with the changing times and stress upon necessary infrastructure and pedagogy modifications to suit the practice.

Kourgiantakis and Lee (2020) discuss the findings of the CASWE (2020) survey (N=3564), where 80% preferred the old style of physical interactive classroom spaces and 61% expressed that learning is hindered in the online mode. During the pandemic, when all normal things appeared most abnormal, students and faculty alike were also grappling with health issues. Training was affected while the need for the services of social workers were on the

rise. They therefore conclude that online social work practice education must: (1) necessarily consider time, workload, curriculum, digital infra structure; (2) advance more research on the effectiveness of digital practice and how to enhance it; (3) adopt the blended mode to counter the changing requirements of the times.

The Digital Shove

Pink, Ferguson and Kelly (2021) do not deny the advent of technology in everyone's lives and in all the professions. But the rapidity and magnitude with which it took over all forms of human interaction during the pandemic and how social work practice was impacted is what they dwell upon. They discuss issues of child protection within the digital framework and make the case for a hybrid practice. They advocate that social work practice must not be encumbered by such uncertainties like the pandemic in future and work towards improvisation to counter all challenges as technology is an inevitable component of advancement. They also emphasize the conventional practice of face-to-face interaction and how in the process, intimate feelings and emotions are encountered. They discuss how in such practices, a continuous engagement with one's sensitivities are essential as the social worker has to anticipate both anxieties as well as risks. Home visits during the pandemic was one that instilled fear to both the practitioner as well as the service recipient. New ways of interaction via digital media were the norm of practice. This challenged their evaluation and practice measures considerably.

With this background, they advocate the hybrid mode of practice, where the home-visit is woven into such a practice. They reiterate that even when digital platforms serve as the interface, there is no denying that the physical world influences it. They distinguish between 'virtual' and 'digital' and cite Hine (2015) to underline how the internet is irrevocably enmeshed with our lives. Hence flexibility and anticipatory social work practice is underlined; where the physical home visit is ingrained within digital practice. This would change the way social work practice can navigate itself in the technology driven future.

A digital ready social work practice is therefore necessary as adopting such online practices are not new despite the advantages and disadvantages. Such new-age practices have also influenced policy making (Cooner et al., 2020; Megele & Buzzi, 2020; Mishna et al., 2012; Reamer, 2013). There is also e-social work which encompasses online research and patient therapy (Lopez Pela'ez and Marcuello-Servos, (2018). Meanwhile Philips (2019) notes the necessity of the digital platform, yet stresses the equal need for a uniform

manner of adopting it in social work practice to avoid discrepancies. Turner (2016) and Taylor (2017) talk about digital literacy amongst practitioners. Mois and Fortuna (2020) make important observations about digital social work in the context of gerontology, where the challenges faced may be quite stark, as against working with young people, who are internet and technology savvy. Jeyashingham (2020) talks about human beings, machines, and digital ware, being all innately wired together in contemporary times.

Nonetheless, Madianou (2020) notes very aptly that hopping on to the digital world brought to the fore a spate of social inequalities and reveals the stark contrast of computer access between the rich and the poor. Humber (2020) also talks about digital inequalities that are influenced by global equations. Golightley and Holloway (2020) discuss how social distancing impeded relationship building and the intimacy requisite in social work practice. Munro (2020) brings in the concept of e-mentoring.

Pink, Ferguson and Kelly (2021) reveal from their empirical studies that since being digitally wired became the norm during the pandemic, the social workers started appreciating how video calls and in-person home visits blended themselves to facilitate the practice. Thus “digital social work” exhibited trust and other emotions that are so essential to the practice. “Digital intimacy” was hence being garnered, where users were showing lesser reluctance to display their emotions on camera. It is however, to be noted that physical home visits necessitated wearing protective cover, face shields, masks etc. during the pandemic. This barrier was withdrawn temporarily, at least in the digital world, where the video call users could see each other clearly. Travel time being done away with, digital interactions were more prolonged and this also gave momentum to building relationships. Simpson et al. (2021) talks about video calls as safer sites to open up for counselling as users shed inhibitions. Thus, the hybrid approach managed to win over the hesitant clients. However, it was also observed that teenagers were more interactive on social media as most of them are already so entwined with it. They even preferred it to a social worker’s physical visit at times. Overall, a hybrid practice was proving fruitful in terms of not being stuck with a case, and also to evade the dangers that the virus posed.

What must be noted is that social workers were upset about the lack of access to the physical world of feel, touch, and smell. Whether the video call or the messaging was not being prompted by someone else besides the client, who was also present in the room simultaneously without the social worker’s knowledge, were matters of concern. In order to fill this vital lacuna in the digital world, in-person contacts were essential. Pink, Ferguson and Kelly

(2021) therefore highlight how hybrid digital social work is the way to go towards the future. They however caution that the experience and potential of the social worker must be considered to assess the outcomes of such a digital practice. Standalone digital social work cannot take down the conventional ways of practice but certainly hybridising the practice will pave the way for social work amidst all contingencies. They nonetheless cite Morozov (2013) to underline the lurking dangers of the tendency to look at technology as the only solace. Madianou (2020) also cautions that everyone must beware of ‘digital capitalism’.

Transformation Within Social Work

So far, we have discussed how social work interventive measures like home visits, for instance, was challenged owing to COVID-19 and the subsequent lockdown, using Cook and Zschomler’s study. Such practice measures necessitate working with distinct human sensitivities to enhance performance and outcome. How the pandemic caught everyone off guard and social work education programs had to re-strategize the field work component has also been discussed (Kourgiantakis & Lee, 2020). Pink, Ferguson & Kelly (2021) also talk about the advent of hybrid field practice. They additionally highlight media inaccessibility and digital inequalities and also caution us about digital capitalism. Thus, the literature review presented here, although limited, advocate a blended pattern of conducting field practice and education. We must also note that these studies were conducted during the pandemic, when lockdowns and “staying away” from physical human contact was best advised. In the face of no other option for contact, the digital world was a panacea for all. What makes it worse is that this panacea was inequitably accessed across geographies. So, the question arises as to whether we are truly digitally ready to transform our practices to suit the changing times even after the pandemic? Are we ready to go hybrid even if not fully digital? These are questions we must weigh seriously. To help us think further, we will look at some typical formats of field practice education used during the pandemic. We shall now look at the Indian scenario, and specifically, with respect to field work education as a university program component. We will also dwell particularly on student-faculty experiences and community perceptions, confined to the department of social work, Assam University, Silchar.

Formats of Field Practice Education During the Pandemic

During the COVID-19 pandemic, schools of social work adopted various contingency measures to cater to the fieldwork practicum. Various formats were practised by the Department of Social Work, Assam University, Silchar, to counter the overwhelming onslaught of the virus on education. These continuity and contingency plans included the following activities.

Online Practice Conversations: Since direct field placement was not possible due to lockdown and social/ physical distancing protocols, experts and practitioners were invited and student trainees were encouraged to discuss the issues and challenges of social work practice in various settings with them. This kind of experience sharing was aimed to inculcate social work competencies among students.

Self-care: Social work trainees as paramedics worked in the frontline helping people in need. Through online platforms such as Zoom, Google Meet, WhatsApp, etc. student trainees were oriented by faculty to be safe from any form of risk, avoid burn-out, stay connected with family, friends and other support systems. This was extremely important in the context of mental health issues.

Skill Training: Online skill labs have been very helpful in imparting skills that are required to develop social work competencies. Although student trainees could not have hands-on experience in applying skills and techniques of social work directly in the field during the pandemic, these skill development programmes enabled them to understand the values of social work (anti-oppressive, equity, human rights etc). The skills and techniques needed for evidence-based practices in various settings were also imparted.

Use of Case Studies: Although it is one of the regular and conventional teaching-learning methods, it has been a very useful tool during the pandemic in facilitating students to acquire a critical understanding of the complexities of practising social work as a profession.

Select Remote Field Activities: Trainees were encouraged to use online tools such as video calls, and various other social media to reach out to their clients and communities.

Tele-counselling: Trainees were involved in tele-counselling activities after receiving due training in the counselling process. Faculties ensured that the do's and don'ts of counselling were well adhered to, as the pandemic was a new challenge to humankind itself.

Online Supervision: Through online individual counselling (IC) and group counselling (GC), trainees were constantly supervised by social work faculties as well as field/agency level supervisors for ethical and professional practices. Apart from practice skills, trainees were encouraged to have reflective and critical thinking about their fieldwork activities through regular report submissions and online IC/GC.

Volunteering: Students also liaised with various non-governmental organisations at local and national levels on the digital platform and rendered their services in multiple ways such as sharing COVID-19 protocol, demystifying the vaccination dilemma, counselling etc.

The various possible practices that were engaged in has been presented above. We have also discussed how a hybrid method is being advocated by other social work scholars. We shall now look at how such a deviation from the physical world on to the digital world affected the teaching learning process. It will help us to reflect whether the digital medium can indeed fill up the vacuum left by physical interactions during the pre-pandemic times, in a remotely placed region like Northeast India.

The Challenges of Digital Field Work

In an environment of no physical interaction being permitted, the digital medium undoubtedly served as a boon to keep the practice going. Likewise, various modalities as discussed above were used to keep the field practice curriculum covered and comply with the rigors of academic programs with minimal compromises.

Counselling is a grand function of social work. However, the perils of reaching out physically either for counselling or for home visits owing to the fear of COVID-19 was high. The initial stigma associated with it also induced people to conceal. The accompanying distrust and fear did not help at all. The steadfast promotion of online learning overlooked the impracticalities of implementing the practical aspects of any curriculum. This was applicable to the physical sciences as well as to social work. The former anyway have confined physical laboratory structures and could tide over the pandemic somehow to an extent. But what of social work? The world is our field. When humans were advised to best remain holed up, where does one practice field work? These were mammoth challenges that had never been countered or envisaged before.

The Additional Problem in the Northeast

Assam University, Silchar, is located in Cachar district in the state of Assam in Northeast India. Effective field work necessitates an abundance of agencies both governmental and non-governmental. Adequately responsive ones are scarce in the region owing to a host of factors. The pandemic made it worse, as most of them were ill prepared to adopt any kind of mentoring for the students. Internet connectivity is another issue. As per the Government of India report (2019), total internet subscribers per 100 population was 48.48%. Rural urban showed a yawning gap with 25.36 for rural and 97.94 for urban in 2019. India's overall position among internet users in the world stood at 141 in 2017. TRAI (2020) notes the total numbers of wireless and wired subscribers at 1,160.52 million as on June 30, 2020. Urban subscribers were pegged at 636.83 million, while rural subscribers were 523.69 million. Down To Earth reports the low numbers of male internet users in the country in the states of Meghalaya (42.1%) and in Assam (42.3%). Female internet users in Assam were just 28.2% (Chari et al., 2020).

Are We Ready for Digital Social Work?

As already indicated above, a multitude of webinars were conducted on a range of topics where practitioners were invited from across India by the department, to share their knowledge and experiences. Department alumni also chipped in to share their practice experiences. It covered very unique and contemporary issues. Some of them are listed here. Design thinking for social innovation, Policy and planning in rural development, Importance of GIS application in rural development with special focus on Adarsh Gram Yojana Project in Assam, Community based disaster risk reduction strategies for local resilience, Field work opportunities for social workers at NIPCCD, Woman and child development with special focus on Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana and POSHAN Abhiyan, Assam, Social entrepreneurship: Leadership & risk management, Nation-wide youth-led movement to strengthen India's battle against COVID-19, Sustainability and future readiness for Grassroots Organisation, Strengthening the vision for National Council for Social Work Education, Border disputes in Northeast India, Emergent challenges in social work, Immunity and health, Pratham's work approach – pre and post covid 19 and Psycho social support & counselling.

Reports on all such webinars were submitted by the students for evaluation. This was in addition to the mandatory IC and GC. Besides this, the volunteering work in any form rendered by the students were also to be submitted as field reports for evaluation. The vexing question was whether it

was sufficient to replace the physical mode of field work. Unfortunately, it did not seem so and the students also expressed how they missed “the feel” of the field. The regular placement agencies for routine field work prior to the pandemic, were either thoroughly embroiled in their own activities, or did not have the wherewithal to mentor students online. The series of lockdowns and the fear of the virus did not help at all to even venture into a hybrid mode.

Field work operates to intersect practice, theory and research. Essential professional training is to be imparted during the process. A homogenised view of all the social sciences does not help the social work curriculum, especially field work. The UGC (2020) proposes a blended mode of teaching learning. It had already launched e-learning platforms such as SWAYAM, MOOCS, e-pathshala, SWAYAMPURABHA, CEC-UGC YouTube channel, National Digital Library, Shodhganga, e-Shodh Sindhu, Vidwan, etc. much before the pandemic. Use of ICTs were also being advocated. Thus, it talks about digital education transforming the teaching learning process in terms of imparting flexibility and quality, catering to students needs and interests, and learning as and when ready, owing to the flexibility implicit in the e-platforms.

What demands attention in social work is the field practicum component. Cook & Zschomler (2020), Kourgiantakis & Lee (2020), and Pink, Ferguson & Kelly (2021) have through empirical studies advocated a blended mode of practice too. Online repositories hardly showed any empirical studies on how field work was taught as a curriculum component during the pandemic. However, webinars and panel discussions were plenty at the local, national and international levels. Research papers on how social work professionals countered their practice challenges during the pandemic were quite large in number, although just a handful has been reviewed in this paper. It must be noted that nations at an advanced stage of development as presented here, namely, England, Canada, etc. will exhibit lesser digital challenges. Studies in the Indian setting were next to unavailable except for one by Dash and Gulalia (2020). They talk about networking amongst schools and departments of social work across the country and sharing experiences amongst faculty and students alike. They also advocate social work journals to encourage documentation of field work experiences during the pandemic, so that it serves as a knowledge base. However, such views are generic and also do not cater to the unique accompanying problems of the digital divide.

Keeping in mind the diversity of the country with huge inequalities between the rich and the poor, the digital inequalities are an inherent characteristic. The northeast problem is even more unique with its typical geographies of

mountainous ranges which interfere with data receptivity. Therefore, merely having an internet subscription as per the TRAI records does not suffice. Besides the problem of data reception, there is also the problem of poverty. According to the economic survey report of the Government of Assam, the gap between the per capita incomes of Assam and India is Rupees 43,468 in current prices, and Rupees 32,158 in constant prices which is quite substantial (G Plus News, 2021). Besides this, rural urban dynamics also play out upsetting any kind of balance. Grinding poverty exists in several parts of the northeast and particularly in Assam. Unfortunately, there is no recorded empirical studies available on the socio-economic background of students pursuing social work in the region. However, anecdotal evidence suggests that a majority of the students pursuing social work are from a lower socio-economic background, barring a few exceptions.

Who will Fill the Learning Gap?

In the eventuality of such counter-currents towards learning, particularly in the field work component, a learning gap is created. How do we fill this up in real time? Do we look at 'Time' itself as a solace? Will it be experience? Or compassion? Whatever one may want to attribute it to, the pandemic has created upheavals in the teaching learning process without a doubt. It has further widened the learning divide between those inhabiting the richer worlds outside the northeast. Do we blame technology? Or the virus? Or accept geography and poverty as the culprit? The tragedy is that such a gap may be carried forward with reeling repercussions to the student community and future social work professionals of the region if we advocate the lion's share of imparting education via digital media. Certainly, it will usher in digital capitalism. Hence, we must exercise due caution while adopting the digital world, whether in the hybrid mode or as a standalone mode, the latter of which appears very inequitable in the current scenario. Digitally induced inequalities should not become intrinsic to the practice, which is against the very ethos of social work practice.

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